

"RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION"

International Conference on Teacher Education

LEARNING STYLES' IMPLICATIONS TO LEARNING AND TEACHING

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola talabalarning o'rganish uslubi va ta'lim uslubiga moslashtirilganliklaridagi yutug'ini baholaydi. Maqolaning asosiy mazmuni o'rganish uslublari va ta'lim uslubi o'rtasidagi munosabatni o'rganishga yo'naltirilgan.

Анотация. В данной статье рассмотрены успеваемость учащихся, когда стратегия обучения соответствует их стилям обучения. В содержание особое внимание уделяется изучению взаимосвязи между стилем обучения и стилем учения.

Annotation. This article evaluates the academic achievement of learners when teaching strategy is matched to their learning styles. It draws main attention to examine the relationship between learning style and teaching style.

Introduction

With different educational and cultural background, different personalities, and different learning experience, everybody differs in his ways of learning a foreign language, which leads to different degrees of success. The different preferred ways all usually referred to as "learning style». The term "learning style" comes from general psychology. So far there is no strong evidence to illustrate which learning style is better than another. According to Dunn and Dunn learning styles model, Learners manifest different learning styles but it is not yet clear whether some styles result in faster and more learning than others. Even though, the models of learning style can still shed some light to the complicated process of learning.

The idea of linking students' learning styles with teaching styles is a widely proposed strategy for teaching. This is the so-called "matching" hypothesis. It suggests that we focus not only on the content of what is to be learnt but on individual learning style characteristics, which should dictate the process of learning. The use of the Learning style inventories and similar instruments are commonly used to match students' learning styles with learning methods. To measure learning styles, Reid designed the Perceptual Learning Styles.

Theoretical Basis

Visual learner

Visual learning style is a style in which the information is visualized in the mind's eye. Most visual learners prefer reading and watching. They find it easier to visualize information rather than just hear about it. Visual learners prefer to use

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graphs and charts also, so they can see what is happening or being taught. The visual learner remembers 75% of what they read or see. Demonstrations from the blackboard, diagrams, graphs and charts are all valuable tools for the visual learner. Generally, analytic visual learners will process the printed word before iconic (pictorial) information. As well, global visual learners will process iconic (pictorial) information before reading the printed text.

Teaching Strategies for the Visual Learner

- Provide lots of interesting visual material in a variety of formats.
- Make sure visual presentations are well-organized.
- During lessons, ensure auditory learners are in a position to hear well.
- Make handouts and all other written work as visually appealing as possible, and easily read.
- Make full use of a variety of technologies: computer, OHP, video camera, live video feeds/close circuit TV, photography, internet, etc.

Auditory learner

Auditory learning style is the style that favors listening. Rather than read about something, these learners prefer to listen. Auditory learners also like to listen to lectures and class discussions. This is because it is easier for them to take in information this way. Write down key points or key words to help avoid confusion due to pronunciation. During lessons, ensure auditory learners are in a position to hear well. Incorporate multimedia applications utilizing sounds, music, or speech (use tape recorders, computer sound cards/recording applications, musical instruments, etc.).

Major Traits of the Auditory Learner

- Remembers verbal instructions well.
- Enjoys the opportunities to present dramatically, including the use of music.
- Finds it difficult to work quietly for long periods of time.
- Easily distracted by noise, but also easily distracted by silence.
- Verbally expresses interest and enthusiasm.
- Enjoys class and group discussions.

Kinesthetic learner

Kinesthetic learning style is a style that involves learning by touching or doing things. Kinesthetic learners may find it easier to make a model rather than just read or just look at the book. Tactile learners prefer touching the information by being creative. The tactile-kinesthetic learner must DO things for them to have the best

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chance of learning. The tactile-kinesthetic learner remembers best the things they experience. Kinesthetic learning involves use of the whole body rather than just hands-on. Getting information from written materials or by listening is not as easy as aforementioned methods.

Teaching Strategies for the Tactile-Kinesthetic Learner

- Allow tactile-kinesthetic students to take breaks during lessons and move around.
- Encourage tactile-kinesthetic students to write down their own notes.
- Encourage tactile-kinesthetic students to stand or move while reciting information or learning new material.
- Incorporate multimedia resources (computer, video camera, OHP transparencies, photography camera, etc.) into programmes (teacher presentations and student presentations).
- Provide lots of tactile-kinesthetic activities in the class.
- Remembers best through getting physically involved in whatever is being learned.

A Match or Mismatch between Learning Styles of the Learners and Teaching Styles of the Teachers has a positive impact on achievement and satisfaction. Students will be more successful if teaching accommodates their preferences. The teaching styles should match students' learning style learners cannot learn effectively when instructional delivery doesn't match their preferred style.

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